

Nimble Artificial Intelligence driven robotic solutions for efficient and self-determined handling and assembly operations.

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Executive summary

The aim of this deliverable is to present the progress of the WP4 developments until the end of the first MASTERLY reporting period.

This document reports the initial version of the developments for tasks 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6. The reported progress includes the following points:

- The developed AR interfaces for providing operator support with instructive information, increasing the operator’s awareness and safety. (LMS)
- The integration of the AR application with AI-based vision systems for a seamless human-robot collaboration. (LMS)
- The developed motion planner for controlling AGVs and navigating with safety and precision. (RWTH)
- The integration of AI-based vision systems developed for T3.2 for cell level robot programming. (LMS)
- The developed motion planner for controlling robotic arms at cell level. (RWTH)
- The human tracking and collision avoidance module for increasing the safety of the operators during the operation at the robotic cell. (LMS)
- The developments of AR application for providing manual robot control of the robotic manipulators and configuring robot settings. (LMS)

Most of these developments will be integrated with other modules and utilized in the demonstrators of the KLEEMANN, DECATHLON, and AERNNOVA use cases.

The future developments for these tasks will be reported in D4.3. The integration of the developments with other systems will be reported in D4.4, while the integration with the workflow controller will be reported in D5.4.

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1 Introduction

This document describes the progress of tasks 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6 for Technical Work Package 4 (WP4) up to the end of the first reporting period (Month 18). These developments aim to provide a complete, flexible, and reconfigurable robotic solution that can be integrated into human-robot collaborative applications, supported by AI-based vision systems and operator support applications.

The general objectives of these developments are focused on:

- Providing innovative methods for information and instruction provision to human operators using AR technology.
- Integrating vision systems with robot programming for picking and assembling different components.
- Controlling mobile manipulators, AGVs, and serial robots to perform various tasks within industrial shop floors.
- Creating seamless methods for manual control of robots and machines, while increasing the safety of human operators and the efficiency of operation execution.

The document is organized into five sections.

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction to the developed functionalities.
- Section 2 focuses on the detailed description of the developments and progress for each task. It is divided into subsections, each corresponding to a specific task as follows:
 - Section 2.1 covers the developments for T4.2.
 - Section 2.2 covers the developments for T4.3.
 - Section 2.3 covers the developments for T4.4.
 - Section 2.4 covers the developments for T4.5.
 - Section 2.5 covers the developments for T4.6.
- Section 3 contains the conclusions of the current deliverable.
- Section 4 presents a list of referenced studies, tools, and libraries used during the development of the presented functionalities.

2 Task related prototypes

2.1 AR interfaces for information visualization and intuitive control

2.1.1 Task overview

This task regards the AR interfaces that have been developed to provide operator support and awareness during the execution of MASTERLY operations. These interfaces enable the establishment of seamless human-robot collaboration. Utilizing the developed AR application, the human operators are informed about the specific tasks they have to perform, with step-by-step instructions supported by visualizations and instructive animations. Also, the operators can interact with these interfaces and send appropriate signals to the robotic and the orchestration systems. Finally, by integrating AI vision systems the AR application can communicate with the orchestration system directly and provide information about the operator's actions.

2.1.2 Adaptive AR-based operator support

2.1.2.1 Introduction

To establish a seamless human-robot collaboration and enhance the user experience with interactive visuals and instructive animations, an AR application was developed for this task using the Unity3D platform. Unity is a powerful software to create applications for various fields of industry, from video games to operator support applications. It offers a varied set of tools to create interactive interfaces utilizing AR technology.

The application was tailored to be executed by egocentric AR glasses devices. To implement the holographic visualization of the interface and the virtual objects, the Mixed Reality ToolKit (MRTK) library was utilized. This library provides certain configurations for adjusting the application to the specific visualization method of the AR glasses and several built-in tools for accessing the sensors of the AR glasses and use their information for numerous applications.

In order to provide appropriate support and information to the operator using the AR application, a connection must be established between the application and the orchestrator system. This connection was facilitated utilizing the ROS 2 framework. Initially, a TCP bridge was established. The AR application serves as the client of the TCP connection and the ROS workspace is responsible for establishing the TCP connection and transmitting the information. This TCP connection was facilitated using the Unity Robotics Hub library, provided by Unity Technologies. In future work, the application will be integrated with the workflow controller using this connection method, for receiving necessary information and sending appropriate signals for executing the operation.

This section describes the interfaces of the AR application and the provided functionalities for enhancing the operator support during the execution of the robotic operations. Section 2.1.2.2 provides a detailed description of the main menu interfaces. Section 2.1.2.3 describes the developed method to localize the virtual objects. Section 2.1.2.4 regards the human-assigned tasks and the developed interfaces for providing information for unexpected events. Finally, Section 2.1.2.5 is focused on the AI-based vision systems to enhance the seamless collaboration between the AR application and the orchestration system.

2.1.2.2 Main menu interface

To enable the operator to navigate through the AR application and access the provided features, a main menu interface was created. This main menu consists of two user interface (UI) elements: the side menu, which refers to a UI element located at a fixed position next to the robotic cell of the current operation and the hand menu which has been designed to follow the operator's hand.

Beginning with the side menu, this UI element has been created to provide to the operator easy access to the most commonly used functionalities of the application during the execution of an operation at the robotic cell. Figure 1 presents the buttons that are contained in this menu.

Figure 1. Side menu interface, (a) UI element to enable the side menu, (b) provided functionalities of the side menu.

More specifically, the menu provides the following options:

- **Robot Control:** This option refers to a specific interface to enable the manual control of the robotic arm. This functionality is linked with task 4.6 and is described in detail in Section 2.5.

- **Application Settings:** This button enables an interface to configure several settings for the application, such as the visibility of the virtual objects or the functionality of the vision systems.
- **Robot Settings:** This UI element provides the operator with several configuration options for the robotic arm, such as the speed and the acceleration of its movements. Similar to the robot control, this functionality is also linked with task 4.6 and explained in Section 2.5.
- **Instructions:** This button refers to a manual of the application. It contains a description of each functionality and how the user can access it.

To design this side menu as convenient and appealing for the operator as possible, two visual effects were also created. The first one refers to an animation to expand or contract the menu, enabling or disabling the UI elements accordingly. This animation allows the user to observe clearly the real-world objects in the robotic cell without any interference of the virtual panels and enables them only when a functionality is needed.

The second visual effect regards the enabling of the buttons' labels. Each button of the side menu has a specific label that explains the corresponding functionality. These labels appear when the operator hovers over the button with their virtual pointer which is an extension of their index finger. This visual effect allows the UI elements to be smaller and depict only the corresponding icons without any static text. These visual effects increase the user experience and the safety of the operation ensuring the clear observation of the surroundings.

The second menu that was created in the AR application is usually called the hand menu. This menu regards a set of similar UI elements that are only appear when the operator gazes at the palm of their hand. Using the hand tracking and the eye gazing of the MRTK library, the application can identify when the operator gazes towards a specific joint of their hand. This menu is automatically disabled when the user of the application looks towards another direction. During this time, menu's UI elements follow the hand of the operator while it is moving. The operator can interact with the elements using their other hand to press the appropriate buttons and activate the provided functionalities. Figure 2 (a) presents the hand menu and the UI elements.

Figure 2. Hand menu interface, (a) hand menu visualization following the operator's hand, (b) example of hand menu interface visualizing the robot settings configuration options.

This menu has been designed for providing a useful interface to the operator regardless of their position within the shopfloor. While the side menu is fixed in a specific position next to the robotic cell, this menu provides useful functionalities that may be needed away from the workstation. As shown in Figure 2 (b) this menu is focused on configuring and controlling the robots. There are four different buttons, two for each robot type: robotic arm and AGV. The one button enables the interfaces for configuring robot settings and the other for manually controlling the pose of the corresponding robot.

2.1.2.3 Interface localization

Within the AR application several virtual objects have been created. Some of these objects are located at fixed positions relative to real-world objects such as the side menu, while others have been designed to follow the operator. In order to match the positions of these visuals in relation to specific real objects such as the robot or the assembly workstation, a localization process must be performed.

To achieve this localization and calibrate the virtual world, a Quick Response (QR) marker detection system was utilized. This marker identification was developed using the QR Tracking module of the MRTK library. This library enables the real-time detection of QR markers within the field of view of the front camera of the AR glasses. To better enhance the performance of the application, a UI element was created to enable and disable the real-time tracking.

To perform the calibration process the following steps are followed. Initially, the operator interacts with the appropriate UI element to enable the real-time QR tracking functionality. After that, the operator approaches the robotic cell and gazes towards a QR marker that has been installed to a specific position in relation to the real objects of the robotic cell. The AR application automatically detects the QR marker. To increase the accuracy of the detection, the application collects 100 samples of the detected positions of the QR code. Each sample contains a translation and an orientation. The translation corresponds to the distance between the position of the QR marker and the start of the coordinate system of the virtual world which is located at the position of the AR glasses the moment the application was initialized. The orientation refers to the rotation of the specific QR marker in relation to the orientation of the AR glasses. These two values are combined calculating a specific pose. Consequently, an average value of the poses of all the samples is calculated. This average value corresponds to the start of a new coordinate system, which is fixed in relation to the real-world objects and same regardless of the exact position of the virtual world coordinate system. Finally, the virtual objects are placed at specific predefined positions in relation to this new coordinate system. These predefined positions can be updated dynamically by the operator to ensure the flexible reconfiguration of the application in case the robotic cell is updated. Figure 3 illustrates the visualization of the detected QR marker, along with the UI element to initialize the calibration process.

Figure 3. QR code identification for interface localization.

2.1.2.4 Human-assigned tasks and unexpected events

One of the most significant functionalities of the AR application is the information provision during the execution of the operations. This information is currently focusing on two main purposes: the human-assigned tasks and the unexpected or safety events.

In the human-robot collaboration applications, there are several tasks assigned for each resource. The basic resources in such operations are the robots and the human operators. To establish a seamless collaboration, the AR application has been enhanced with the necessary interfaces to inform the operator about the task that have to perform at each step of the procedure. This information is received by the orchestration system, which is responsible of assigning tasks to each resource during execution.

To enhance the user experience of the application and provide the optimal support to each operator, two different modes were designed for visualizing the human-assigned tasks: the experienced and the inexperienced mode. The inexperienced mode has been designed for operators who are not totally aware of the exact process for the execution of the operation and need constant assistance for performing the tasks. In this mode, detailed instructions for the operator are provided by the orchestration system to the AR application. These instructions contain textual information and ID numbers that correspond to specific components which should be installed on the assembly workstation. The application receives this information, displays the textual instructions on a user interface and place a visualization of the component in the exact position where the operator should install it. Figure 4 presents the information visualization with (a) textual information and (b) virtual object for component visualization.

Figure 4. Inexperienced mode human-assign task, (a) textual information, (b) visual indicator.

As shown in Figure 4 (a), the interface that visualizes the textual information provides also two virtual buttons: “Task Completed” and “Task Rejected”. These buttons have been designed to send the appropriate signals to the orchestration system for either completing a task or rejecting it in case the operator decides that it cannot be performed at that moment. The orchestration system can use this information to organize and send the future tasks to the available resources.

The second mode has been designed for more experienced operators that can perform the whole process of the operation with no significant assistance. In this case, the AR application provides information, visualizations and indicators seamlessly, without any interaction by the operator and can be adapted to the operator’s actions dynamically. This functionality provides limited support to the operator ensuring at the same time that the cycle time of the operation will not be increased due to unnecessary interactions of the operator with the AR interfaces. To achieve this, an AI-based vision system was developed using the cameras that are installed on the AR glasses. This vision system detects the components that are grasped by the operator and communicates automatically with the orchestration system. The implementation of the vision system is described in detail in the following subsection (2.1.2.5).

Figure 5. Human-assigned tasks communication architecture, (a) notifications for correct and incorrect component selection, (b) detection of component and task assignment process

The basic architecture of the connection between the AR application and the orchestration system to facilitate the information provision for the human-assigned tasks is presented in Figure 5. In order to facilitate the proper communication between these modules the following procedure has been designed. Initially, the operator picks a specific part to proceed with the assembly. The vision system automatically detects the grasped component and informs the orchestration system with the component ID. The orchestrator system communicates with the database where the information about all these components is stored and checks if the current grasped component should be installed at the moment. For the KLEEMANN case, the orchestration system retrieves information from the database regarding which component should be installed to each din rail. In case the detected part can be installed on the specific chosen din rail, the orchestration system sends a human-assigned task for installing the component at the correct position, as presented in Figure 4. From the other hand, if the operator has picked an invalid component, the orchestration system informs them with the corresponding textual notification and a red visual is enabled to ensure an incorrect installation, as depicted in Figure 6. The left side of Figure 5 illustrates the interfaces for the two different cases: correct and incorrect component selection.

Figure 6. Visual indicator for incorrect component selection.

Apart from the human-assigned tasks, the AR application can also receive notifications about specific unexpected or safety events. These notifications are also sent by the orchestration system, to inform the operator about important scenarios and enable them to select how the execution will be proceeded. For visualizing this information, another interface was created similar to the one of the human-assigned

tasks. Figure 7 presents an example of this kind of notifications, where the operator is informed about status of the mobile robot's battery.

Figure 7. Example of an unexpected event notification.

As shown in the figure, this interface has two UI elements. The button with the “Resume” label, grants access to the orchestration system to proceed with the normal operation, while the “Cancel” button, stops the execution and send the signal to proceed with a recovery process. By implementing this interface, the operator can be aware of any events may occur during the execution avoiding any safety issues.

2.1.2.5 Intuitive control based on AI vision systems

As explained in the previous section; in order to provide efficient support using AR technology, it was essential to develop a method for accurately identifying objects grasped by the operator. This AI-based vision system utilizes the ROS2 network to facilitate precise data communication between concurrently running nodes, enabling multitasking. These nodes include an image publisher for the AR glasses and a detection system node. By accurately detecting the item currently in the operator's hands, the orchestration system can deliver relevant tasks for the operator to complete the assembly process.

The initial step involved creating a node to transfer the AR stream to the ROS network. This node utilizes the HL2SS library to establish an active TCP connection with the AR glasses, providing essential parameters such as camera size and frame rate. While running, this node waits for valid data packets from the connection. Upon receipt, it transforms them into the equivalent ROS Image message. Finally, the message is published to a topic within the network. This operation serves as an intermediary between the AR glasses and ROS, allowing for real-time modifications to data quality and settings.

Subsequently, a method was employed to focus the image on the operator's hand using an AI model. Detecting parts within the entire image would result in multiple detections, including items currently in the box or on the table. To address this, a machine learning model was implemented to specifically scan for the operator's hands. The MediaPipe Hands library, which offers high-fidelity hand and finger tracking, was used. This model has minimal impact on performance and produces 21 landmarks for each hand. Once the model identifies the operator's hand, a black mask is applied over the image, leaving only the area occupied by the detected hand visible. The mask placement is dynamic and adjusts in size according to the hand's distance from the camera. This method minimizes the search area for detection to the operator's palm, thereby filtering out irrelevant parts and enhancing both performance and accuracy. Figure 8 presents the viewport of the front camera of the AR glasses along with the filtering of the image following the hand tracking process.

Figure 8. Filtering the camera image using hand tracking.

The most critical step in this process is accurately identifying the grasped part using an AI detection model. This AI module utilizes a state-of-the-art Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on a custom dataset. The model is designed to accurately track and identify parts against varying backgrounds, often partially occluded by the human hand. The implementation based on the YOLOv8 architecture ensures precise inference within the visible portion of the image, enabling reliable identification of the grasped part.

The creation of the custom dataset is a two-part process designed to meet two specific criteria. The first part involves the general identification of parts, utilizing the dataset from the CAD-based object detection module (described in D3.1), which has already yielded excellent results. The second part involves augmenting this dataset with additional images captured using the AR glasses camera. These images include parts occluded by the operator's hand in various positions and orientations. The datasets were then merged and randomized to ensure optimal performance during training.

Following this, a ROS node was developed to deploy the aforementioned methods in real-time using the AR stream. The structure of the detection node is as follows:

- Capture the latest frame from the stream.
- Perform hand model inference.
- Place a mask on the frame.
- Perform detection model inference.

Once the pipeline is completed and the results are obtained, a filtering step is implemented. To prevent multiple detections, only the object with the highest confidence is retained. Simultaneously, a system verifies that the same part type has been consistently detected for a specified convergence time before publishing it via a topic to avoid erroneous detections. Finally, the identified part type is broadcasted, enabling the orchestration system to assign the most appropriate task to the operator as explained in the previous subsection. Figure 9 presents the architecture of the sensor streaming, the prediction of the grasped components and the communication with the orchestration system.

Figure 9. AR glasses sensor streaming and component prediction architecture.

2.1.3 Role in pilot cases

As mentioned in previous sections, the AR application will be used within the scope of MASTERLY to provide operator support and enhance the human-robot collaboration applications. The application will be applied in KLEEMANN and AERNNOVA cases. In KLEEMANN case, the operator will receive information from the workflow controller for the assembly of the electrical cabinet. In AERNNOVA case, the AR application will provide a visualization of the result of the vision systems in order to guide them to perform a manual guidance operation. In DECATHLON case, the AR application is not applied, since a human-robot collaboration is not required.

2.2 Automated programming of AGVs

2.2.1 Task overview

In Task 4.3, RWTH Aachen University, with support from IIT and LMS, is developing motion planning algorithms for AGVs used in production lines. The algorithm will calculate trajectories for AGVs, considering the environment, the trained motion primitives, and task allocation from Task 3.4. Furthermore, RWTH is developing fine-localization and fine-positioning techniques to enable AGVs to approach humans and production cells with greater precision. These methods utilize closed-loop control using external markers and environmental features. The initial validation of the algorithms will be conducted by RWTH with their own AGVs.

2.2.2 Motion primitive based mobile platform control

AGVs have become a cornerstone of modern production lines, significantly enhancing operational efficiency and flexibility. To optimize the performance and versatility of AGVs, advanced motion planning algorithms are essential. This chapter delves into the developed approach for AGV control based on Dynamic Motion Primitives (DMPs). The focus lies on the development and implementation of this approach to ensure precise and adaptable trajectory execution. The chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the requirements and basics on DMPs and potential field method, the trajectory generation process, the collision avoidance strategy and first test results.

2.2.2.1 Requirements and system definition

The development of an advanced motion planning algorithm for AGVs addresses several critical requirements. The system must be capable of calculating optimal trajectories for AGVs by considering

environmental factors and training use case specific motion primitives. The AGVs are integrated into collaborative assembly processes, working alongside human operators. The requirements extend to ensuring seamless Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC), with algorithms designed to consider the human operator's condition and to implement collision avoidance measures. This setup necessitates a high level of adaptability and precision, facilitated by the motion planning.

2.2.2.2 Basics on dynamic motion primitives

Dynamic Motion Primitives (DMPs) are a method for trajectory control and planning, developed to represent complex motor actions flexibly and stably without extensive manual parameter tuning. DMPs conceptualize complex movements as sequences or combinations of primitive actions, formalized as nonlinear dynamical systems. They are classified into two types: discrete and rhythmic, with the focus here on discrete DMPs.

A discrete DMP uses point attractor dynamics to guide the system towards a target goal. The system's state y is influenced by a goal g and includes a nonlinear forcing term f that adjusts the trajectory dynamically. The canonical system, defined by simple decay dynamics, drives the forcing function, ensuring that the trajectory naturally scales over time and space. This design enables DMPs to generalize movements to different goals and speeds. τ is the time constant and α_z and β_z positive constants. The DMP formulation resembles a spring dampener system. Therefore, the natural behaviour of this system always ensures that the goal is reached. The formulation is extended by a coupling term C_t that is used for adapting the trajectory due to collision obstacles.

$$\tau \tau \dot{y} = \alpha_z (\beta_z (g - y) - \dot{y}) + f + C_t$$

Key components of discrete DMPs include the forcing term, basis functions, and temporal and spatial scaling factors. The forcing term f is constructed using Gaussian basis functions activated as the canonical system evolves. Spatial scaling ensures the trajectory adapts to different goal distances, while temporal scaling allows the system to follow the same path at varying speeds.

To imitate a desired path, the desired trajectory's acceleration is calculated and used to determine the necessary forcing function. Optimization techniques, such as locally weighted regression, are employed to adjust the weights of the basic functions, allowing the system to approximate complex trajectories accurately. Overall, DMPs provide a robust framework for generating adaptable and stable trajectories, making them suitable for various applications in robotics and automated systems.

2.2.2.3 Basics on potential field method for collision avoidance

The Potential Field method is a traditional and fundamental algorithm used for obstacle detection and path planning in robotics. This algorithm assigns an artificial potential field to every point in the world, guiding the robot from areas of higher potential to lower potential, ultimately towards the goal. In a 2D space, the goal node has the lowest potential, while the starting node has the highest. Two types of potential fields are generated: attractive fields, which are associated with the goal, and repulsive fields, which are generated by obstacles to keep the AGV away from them.

The force of attraction pulls the AGV towards the goal, calculated using the coordinates of the starting and goal nodes. The force of repulsion pushes the AGV away from obstacles and boundaries. The repulsive force by obstacles is a function of the distance from the AGV to the obstacles, while the repulsive force by boundaries is uniform throughout the system. The total force at any point in the environment is the sum of the attractive and repulsive forces.

Despite its usefulness, the Potential Field method has some limitations. It performs poorly in narrow passages and dynamic environments and is prone to local minima traps. Additionally, it has difficulty dealing with symmetrical obstacles.

In summary, while the Potential Field method offers a reasonable solution time for obstacle avoidance, it struggles with local minima and non-optimal results. The choice of path-planning algorithm should consider the specific operational requirements, balancing between computational time and optimality.

2.2.2.4 Motion planning process

The developed motion planning process is depicted in Figure 10. It is divided into two phases: the training phase and the execution phase. Initially, a representative trajectory that the AGV should follow is defined. Using this defined trajectory, the DMP is trained. This training process establishes the necessary parameters and the forcing function that will guide the system to follow the desired path. Once the DMP is trained, it is ready for use during the execution phase.

In the execution phase, the trained DMP is utilized for trajectory generation. The system first checks if any adaptation is required. Adaptations may be necessary for collision avoidance, adjusting start/goal points, or modifying the execution time due to changes in the environment or task requirements. If no adaptation is needed, the process moves directly to trajectory generation. If adaptation is required, the system adjusts the trajectory accordingly.

Based on the trained DMP, the system generates the trajectory that the AGV will follow. This generated trajectory is then represented in a suitable format for execution. For the initial prototype, the generated trajectory is saved as a .txt-file for later execution on the real AGV by the ROS controller.

Figure 10. Motion Planning Process.

2.2.2.5 Collision avoidance strategy

Figure 11 shows the collision avoidance process. It begins by measuring the distance d between the object and the robot. This distance is then compared with a threshold distance d_0 . If d is greater than or equal to d_0 , the repelling torque τ_{rep}^k , the transformed force that is inserted as a coupling term into the DMP formulation, is set to zero, indicating no collision threat. However, if d is less than d_0 , the process moves forward to calculate the repelling force $\vec{F}_{rep}^k = \frac{1}{2} \delta \left(\frac{1}{d} - \frac{1}{d_0} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{d^2} \cdot \vec{u}$, which acts to push the robot away from the object to avoid a collision, where \vec{u} is the unit vector between the obstacle and the nearest point of the robot and δ a constant. The repelling force must be transformed into joint space for the DMP formulation. Subsequently, the transposed Jacobian J_k^T is computed, which relates the velocities

and forces in joint space to those in Cartesian space. Finally, the repelling torque τ_{rep}^k is determined using the formula $\tau_{rep}^k = J_k^T \cdot \overrightarrow{F_{rep}^k}$. This torque is applied to the robot joints to generate the necessary movement to prevent a collision. This approach ensures that the robot maintains a safe distance from objects by calculating and applying appropriate forces and torques based on the proximity to objects within its environment. Furthermore, the collision model of the robot is simplified to meet real-time capability requirements (see Figure 12).

Figure 11. Collision avoidance strategy.

Figure 12. Collision model simplification of AGV SUMMIT-XL STEEL.

2.2.2.6 First test results

The first validation phase conducted by RWTH involves using their AGV to test and refine the motion planning algorithm. The initial test includes a SUMMIT-XL STEEL that is to be driven up to a platform or defined position. Additionally, the collision avoidance is tested.

Figure 13 shows the first test results of the trajectory planner. The dashed blue line symbolizes the trajectory used to train the DMP. The green solid line shows an adapted trajectory to a new target using the trained DMP. Finally, the orange solid line shows the generated trajectory obtained using the combination of DMP motion planning and collision avoidance by the potential field method. The combination of both approaches resembles a trajectory that is not desired. On the one hand, the AGV does not reach its target position. This is due to the lack of a fine localization and positioning module that will be developed in the next project phase. Due to the slip of the mecanum wheels, the positioning accuracy of the platform is not precise enough. On the other hand, the trajectory oscillates. This is due to the simplification of the collision model and can be neglected by finer discretization of the robot model.

Figure 13. First test results of DMP motion planner for AGVs.

2.2.2.7 Future work

The next phase of Task 4.3 focuses on developing a fine-localization and -positioning approach, along with the integration of the MoveBase framework. Fine-localization and -positioning will improve the position accuracy of the AGV using semantic features of the environment and reflective markers. Additionally, RWTH develops use case-specific motion primitives for AGVs. These motion primitives will be tailored to meet the requirements of the KLEEMANN use case. Finally, RWTH tests the developed motion primitives on their premises.

2.2.3 Role in pilot cases

In the KLEEMANN use case, task 4.3 supports the planning of movements for mobile manipulators, comprising both a serial robot and an AGV. In this context, the system is employed in the assembly of electrical cabinets, working alongside human operators to guarantee precise positioning and attachment of components onto the back panel. Moreover, it promotes seamless HRC by considering the condition of the human operator and implementing measures for collision avoidance. In task 4.3, the algorithms for motion planning and fine localization of the AGVs are developed.

In the DECATHLON and AERNNOVA use cases, the motion planner for AGVs is not yet utilized/applicable.

2.3 Automated cell level robot programming exploiting CAD models of parts

2.3.1 Task overview

This task is responsible for the implementation of a module intended to enhance robot programming efficiency by leveraging CAD file data of various objects within a scene. Specifically, the methodologies developed within this task take into consideration the robot gripper configuration and the geometry of the 3D models of the objects. This enables the automatic processing of CAD files to extract valuable information, facilitating the implementation and training of a vision-based deep learning network capable of precise and robust grasping point estimation on the surfaces of the objects. Below a detailed description of the key points of the proposed module are provided.

2.3.2 CAD based robot programming

2.3.2.1 CAD processing

To obtain the desired characteristics of the objects present in a scene, a prior-processing procedure is required. The objective is to identify regions suitable for a smooth grip based on the geometry of each object and the design of the grasping tool. To achieve this, the approach takes into consideration a suction-based gripping end effector mounted on a robotic arm that can be used for manipulating the components. In general suction grippers excel in grasping objects with smooth, flat or curved surfaces. Their effectiveness lies in their ability to create a vacuum seal between the gripper and the object, generating a strong holding force. This is particularly advantageous for objects that may be difficult to grasp using traditional mechanical grippers, such as those with irregular shapes or fragile structures. However, the dynamic component manipulation with suction cup requires the analysis of the different existing geometries appearing in a scene in order to identify the seal-forming areas. Consequently, the processing of CAD files become an indispensable procedure, as they can be useful source of information for extracting the necessary geometric data. To demonstrate the adaptability of the module, proposed under Task 4.4, which is a key focus area of the MASTERLY project, four different components of varying sizes, shapes, and weights have been selected, as displayed in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Actual components candidates for CAD based robot programming module.

In general, the efficient operation of a suction gripper, requires two key elements: the identification of a suitable point on the candidate object's surface where the gripper will be positioned, and the determination of the direction from which the gripper will approach the object. To obtain this crucial information, the mesh of the object can be utilized, as it contains details of all points along with their respective normals, which are vectors pointing outward from the corresponding surfaces. These normals can therefore be used to determine the optimal picking direction. This way, each point can be considered as a potential candidate for grasping, given that certain criteria are met. However, to ensure that the final selected grasping points will cover all the object's graspable area efficiently, dense point representations are essential. This requirement isn't always met by CAD files, as they typically prioritize providing the geometric attributes with a minimal number of points to prevent large file sizes. To address this, the proposed approach employs a uniform resampling technique to enhance the density of the vertices (points) and evenly distribute them through the object geometry maintaining its overall shape and structure (Figure 15).

Figure 15: (a) The mesh for a candidate object, (b) the original representation from the CAD file and (c) the output of the uniform resampling procedure.

Having a dense representation of point clouds allows for the selection of grasping points capable of covering the entire surface area of a candidate object. However, to identify points conducive to forming a seal with the suction cup, an evaluation process is necessary. This involves determining whether a candidate point resides on a relatively smooth surface or not. To accomplish this, the methodology requires the radius of the suction cup intended for manipulation, enabling the creation of a copy of it within a simulation environment to observe its interaction with objects. This process is automated through an algorithm responsible for labelling the meshes of objects based on their graspable regions. The algorithm takes as input the dense representation of an object and the simulated suction cup, and outputs a ratio of the total number of points of the object, along with a grasping quality score between $[0, 1]$ for each one. To visually assess the chosen grasping points for an object along with their corresponding scores, an algorithm has been developed. Its main purpose is to display the suction cup as a cylinder at each selected point, with the colour indicating the score's proximity to 1. A greener cylinder suggests higher likelihood of the point facilitating a seal formation and successfully grasped by the robot (Figure 16b).

Figure 16: (a) Score assignment procedure for two given points and (b) visualization of a sample of the final annotated points.

2.3.2.2 Synthetic dataset

Having the grasping points for a given object is a good start towards building a dataset dedicated for training a vision-based deep learning model responsible for estimating these points on the actual components in real-time and for any given object position. However, the acquisition and the annotation of such data is usually a labour costly and difficult procedure, as it requires the knowledge of the object 6D poses with respect to the vision sensor's coordinate system. To avoid this, the present methodology employs the generation of synthetic data using Blender and Python. Specifically, the BlenderProc package is utilized and further enhanced in order to host the parts and scenes that are represented in the context of MASTERLY. This package contains useful algorithms for generating RGB-D data based on pre-defined camera configurations. For each rendered data, annotations are also provided in terms of object masks, bounding boxes and 6D poses.

To fully leverage the benefits of the package and produce a dataset closely mirroring real-world, a precise description and representation of the actual world within the simulation environment is essential. In the terms of MASTERLY needs, such an environment could be consisted of the following key components (Figure 17):

- An assembly workstation, responsible for marking the working area and housing the bin.
- A variable-intensity light source positioned randomly to introduce lighting variations in the captured data.
- A randomized background plane serving as the backdrop for all scene elements.
- A container box designed to accommodate the parts needed for dataset generation.
- A random background plane where all the objects of the scene are placed.
- Multiple objects of interest placed at random position and orientations within the container box.
- A virtual camera responsible for capturing the objects of interest and generating the dataset.

Figure 17: Virtual scene for synthetic data generation in Blender environment.

In order to capture analytical data covering various scenarios, the final dataset consists of numerous scenes, each comprising multiple rendered frames. Within each scene, objects of interest are initially

positioned above the box container. To simulate real-world dynamics, physics simulators are utilized to replicate the forces such as gravity and component collisions. Consequently, as the simulation starts, the objects naturally fall into the bin, acquiring their final positions. Moreover, each object within every scene as well as the background plane are assigned of a random material. This ensures the dataset's capacity to enforce the generalization capabilities of the proposed deep learning model. To capture the required information, a virtual camera with identical intrinsic parameters to the real one is employed. This camera is the only element that moves between frames, and it is always positioned above the container box, with its field of view directed towards the desired objects. The camera movement is occurring for capturing the objects from different points of view, which is necessary for having a strong and generic dataset with a variety of 6D object poses.

Since all the described elements are located inside the Blender environment, their positions relative to the origin axis are known. Therefore, the relative pose of a selected object with respect to the camera system can also be obtained, as explained in section 5.2 of deliverable D3.1. These poses are calculated individually for each object and frame, and they are subsequently saved in JSON files specific to each scene. Additionally, for each frame, RGB and depth images are captured, along with 2D masks of the objects and their corresponding bounding boxes (Figure 18). All these data can be used to train a variety of deep learning models for several tasks like object detection, semantic segmentation or 6D pose estimation. In this case the latter is required since the focus is on obtaining 3D grasping points on top of object surfaces.

Figure 18: Synthetic dataset visualization (a) the RGB image, (b) depth image, (c) object masks and (d) bounding boxes and object 6D poses.

2.3.2.3 Combination of vision algorithms

To effectively manage grasping point and object detection models while communicating with the orchestrator system, a ROS2 server was developed. This server includes an action server, subscribers, publishers running in separate threads, and the AI models. While having suction points or bounding boxes is vital, a final module capable of merging this information was needed to create a synergistic vision system. To address this, a filtering step was implemented. Using this architecture, the AI models

are integrated into ROS2, enabling communication with the orchestrator system. Below is a detailed explanation of the server architecture:

When the server node is launched, subscribers begin capturing RGB and Depth data from the camera topics, and the AI models are initialized. Once the orchestrator system triggers the action callback, both inference and detection start using the same camera frame. The results are then passed through the filtering step. Each valid suction point is assigned to a detected item by comparing the suction point's pixel coordinates to the pixel area covered by each bounding box. The suction point with the highest confidence is selected as the final point, and the others are discarded. Finally, a list containing all individual items and their information is returned to the orchestrator system for selecting the target item. Figure 19 presents the architecture of the combination of vision algorithms, the generation of the ROS frame and the communication with the orchestration system to successfully perform robot programming.

Figure 19. Combination of vision systems and robot programming architecture.

2.3.2.4 Frame generation in ROS2

To be able to achieve component grasping and manipulation through ROS2 and Moveit2, a method is needed to translate the generated grasping point information into actual frames corresponding to real 3D space. A frame refers to a coordinate system used for representing the position and orientation of objects within a robotic system, facilitating accurate spatial relationships and transformations between different components. The data collected from the grasping point model's output is a 1x7 Vector, as explained in D3.1, containing the confidence score, the translational X, Y, Z data and the rotational data in the form of normal X, normal Y and normal Z. Though manipulation of this data a rotation matrix can be extracted stemming from the camera's optical frame. A rotation matrix is a mathematical tool used to describe the rotation of an object in three-dimensional space, typically represented as a square matrix that preserves the lengths of vectors and angles between them during the rotation process.

A ROS2 action server had to be set up for performing the necessary calculations and for publishing the resulted frame in the ROS2 network. A ROS 2 action server is a component that manages the execution of long-running tasks or goals within a robotic system, providing a structured communication interface for clients to send requests, monitor progress, and receive feedback or results asynchronously. The sequence of events with the server is defined as:

- First the server accepts the action goal containing the information of the target grasping point.
- Secondly it performs the mathematical calculations for extracting the rotation matrix.
- Thirdly it calculates the rotation matrix from a given parent frame.
- Fourthly the server initializes a ros2 broadcaster and publishes the resulted target frame.
- Finally, it returns the result of the operation to the client.

For the calculation of the rotation matrix the following steps are used. The translation part of the input vector is directly applied in the matrix as it is extracted from the camera point cloud and contains valid information. Regarding the rotation the goal is to transform the normals vector into quaternion. Quaternions are mathematical constructs used to represent rotations in three-dimensional space, offering advantages over traditional Euler angles due to their avoidance of gimbal lock and their ability to provide more stable and efficient calculations for orientation in robotics, computer graphics, and other fields. Regarding the translation a certain mathematical method had to be applied for transforming the normals into quaternion. The implemented method starts by normalizing the input normal vector to ensure it only represents direction. Then, it defines the up vector $[0, 0, 1]$ and calculates the rotation axis by taking the cross product between the up vector and the normalized normals vector, normalizing the result to ensure it has unit length. The rotation angle is determined using the arccosine of the dot product between the up vector and the normalized normal vector. The last step involves constructing the quaternion representation of the rotation using the axis-angle method. The rotation axis is then scaled by the rotation angle. This multiplication yields a vector representing the rotation, which is then used to generate the quaternion representing the rotation required to align the given normal vector with the positive z-axis. This rotational data originates from the camera frame but must be published through a specified parent frame. The rotation matrix describing the transformation from the camera frame to the target frame is extracted from this data. Using ROS, the quaternion and translation data from the parent frame to the camera frame are obtained, enabling the creation of another rotation frame that describes this exact transformation. Finally, by multiplying the rotation matrices, the rotation from the parent frame to the target frame is determined. From this resulting rotation matrix, the translation and quaternion can be extracted. After the calculation are finished a ros2 transform instance is created and passed the necessary information such as the translation, resulted rotation, name and the parent frame and broadcasted into the ROS2 network as a frame.

This method creates frames in actual three-dimensional space from grasping point data, making robot operation easier. The system receives input with target grasping point data through a ROS2 action server, computes rotation matrices, and broadcasts the resulting frames into the ROS2 network. Through the conversion of normals into quaternions, the system allows precise orientation detection for tasks involving robotic manipulation. The fluid combination of data processing and frame generation augments the robot's capacity to discern and engage with its surroundings. Figure 20 presents examples of the frame generation using the combined vision systems.

Figure 20. Frame generation from the result of vision systems.

2.3.2.5 Robot path programming

The foundation for controlling the robotic arm is the MoveIt 2 package, the robotic manipulation platform for ROS 2. MoveIt 2 integrates the latest advancements in motion planning, manipulation, 3D perception, kinematics, control, and navigation. This package provides a wide array of features and low-level commands for initiating and controlling a move group.

For bin picking, a sequence of movements is set to establish a plan, assuming the target frame has already been generated. First, the robotic arm moves to a pose opposed to the target frame, with an offset in the Z axis so that the suction gripper faces the targeted part. Next, a Cartesian movement is initiated along the Z axis, allowing the gripper to move towards the part, eliminating the offset, and creating a seal with the surface of the part. The suction gripper is then activated to attach the part. Finally, an opposite Cartesian movement is executed to remove the part from the bin without hitting any obstacles. The use of Cartesian movements ensures the path is safe from collisions caused by inverse kinematics abnormalities. This sequence provides a reliable method for automatically grasping parts, given that the target frame is accurate. Figure 21 illustrates the robot movement towards generated frames in RVIZ2 environment.

Figure 21. Robot programming to generated frame using the result of the combined vision systems.

To streamline movements, an action server was developed. The orchestration system sends an action containing relevant information for path generation, such as the movement type and final pose. The

server accepts the goal and creates the trajectory by utilizing the corresponding lower-level MoveIt 2 code. Concurrently, as the trajectory is executed, specific topics are published, providing information such as the future trajectory of the end effector. Finally, the server activates the relevant ROS 2 controllers and publishes the goal trajectory with an action request. This system ensures adaptability and efficiency, allowing real-time modifications by the orchestration system. The action server functions as a wrapper for MoveIt 2, facilitating seamless integration and execution of movements. Figure 22 presents the architecture of ROS communication for successfully execute robot movements using MoveIt 2.

Figure 22. ROS communication for the execution of robot movements.

2.3.3 Role in pilot cases

This section describes the CAD processing, the simulation of suction gripper and the creation of the synthetic scene for the grasping points estimation, along with the combination of vision algorithms for the successful CAD-based robot programming. All these developments will be integrated for the KLEEMANN case. They will be utilized for picking the components from the box container and install them on the electrical cabinet.

In DECATHLON and AERNNOVA cases, these developments are not yet utilized/applicable.

2.4 Automated cell level robot programming using physical artefacts

2.4.1 Task overview

In Task 4.5, RWTH Aachen University is developing motion primitives for serial robots and mobile manipulators in production cells. These primitives are organized by an optimization algorithm that considers several factors, including object characteristics, gripper attributes, task dependencies, and environmental status. The algorithm generates adaptable trajectories, drawing on data from the vision system in Task 3.2 and task planner in Task 3.4. Task 4.5 includes integration into the MoveIt frameworks as a new plugin for motion planning. LMS assists with task planning integration and the development of a human tracking module for avoiding the human operator during the generation of robot's trajectories.

2.4.2 Motion primitives based robotic arm control

The development of motion primitives for robotic arm control in production cells involves methodologies that enhance the adaptability of robotic operations and the ease of use for programming motions. This section presents the requirements and system descriptions integral to this task, focusing on the application of DMPs and potential field methods.

The motion planning process is optimized by an algorithm that incorporates object characteristics, gripper attributes, task dependencies, and environmental conditions. The integration of data from the vision system in Task 3.2 and the task planner from Task 3.4 ensures that the generated trajectories are both precise and adaptable.

A detailed exploration of the theoretical foundations, including dynamic motion primitives and potential field methods was already provided in Section 2.2.2. This section covers the specific collision avoidance strategy for robotic arms. First test results are presented to demonstrate the practical effectiveness of the developed DMP motion planner for robotic arm control.

2.4.2.1 Requirements and system description

The development of motion primitives for robotic arm control in production cells involves creating a system that enables precise and adaptable control of robotic arms. Essential requirements include seamless integration with the vision system from Task 3.2 and the task planner from Task 3.4, ensuring real-time adaptability. The algorithm must consider object characteristics, gripper attributes, task dependencies, and environmental status to generate adaptable motion trajectories. Robust collision avoidance strategies are crucial for safe operation alongside human operators.

The system architecture includes a robotic arm with six degrees of freedom and a versatile gripper attached to its flange. The vision system provides real-time environmental data for pick and place poses and movements of the human operator, crucial for adapting motion primitives. The task planner guides the operations sequence, aiding the algorithm in generating appropriate trajectories. The system is designed for integration into the MoveIt framework, ensuring a user-friendly interface by using existing ROS standards.

2.4.2.2 Basics on dynamic motion primitives

The basics on dynamic motion primitives were already described in Section 2.2.2.2.

2.4.2.3 Basics on potential field method for collision avoidance

Section 2.2.2.3 already introduced the basics on potential field method for collision avoidance.

2.4.2.4 Motion planning process

The motion planning process for robotic arms takes place analog to the motion planning process for AGVs (see Section 2.2.2.4). The difference is the dimension of the motion primitive. While AGVs have three degrees of freedom (DoF) to move on a plane, robotic arms usually have six DoF. The motion primitive approach works with multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is possible to employ the developed approach on multiDoF systems (e.g., robotic arms with seven DoF or mobile manipulators as combination of an AGV and a robotic arm with nine DoF).

2.4.2.5 Collision avoidance strategy

The collision avoidance strategy for robotic arms is analog to the one described in Section 2.2.2.5. Instead of collision avoidance for an AGV, the collision of the robotic arm must be avoided. Therefore, the simplified collision model depicted in Figure 23 (a) is employed. Figure 23 (b) shows the effect of a repelling force on the robot structure in form of moments in the robot axis.

Figure 23. Collision model simplification of robotic arm UR5 (a) and effect of the repelling force on the robot joint moments (b).

2.4.2.6 Initial test results

The first validation phase conducted by RWTH involves using their robotic arm to test and refine the motion planning algorithm. The initial test includes a Universal Robot UR5 that moves to a pick position in a downwards movement.

Figure 24 shows the first test results of the trajectory planner. The dashed blue line symbolizes the trajectory used to train the DMP. The green and orange solid lines show two adapted trajectories with different start and goal positions using the trained DMP.

Figure 24. First test results of DMP motion planner for robotic arms.

Figure 25 demonstrates the execution of trajectories without and with collision avoidance using the potential field method. The UR5 robot avoids a point collision object but the repelling force of the point object introduces jerk into the end-effector trajectories, which is not advantageous for the trajectory execution. Additionally, the repelling force of the collision object continues to act on the robot even after the object has been bypassed. This leads the trajectory being excessively deflected (see Figure 25 (a)).

Figure 25. Robotic arm trajectory without collision avoidance (dashed line) and with collision avoidance (solid line).

2.4.2.7 Future work

The upcoming phase of Task 4.5 includes the development of use case-specific motion primitives, which will be essential for addressing the diverse requirements of the KLEEMANN and DECATHLON use cases. This development will be accompanied by testing to understand when a new motion primitive needs to be trained and to identify optimal parameter sets for different use cases. These tests will help refine the system's adaptability and efficiency and are conducted on RWTH premises. Additionally, the integration of the motion planner into the MoveIt framework must be completed. This integration will enhance the motion planning capabilities of the system, allowing for user friendly control of robotic arms.

2.4.3 Robot control based on human perception

2.4.3.1 Human Tracking

Accurately detecting human whereabouts in real-time is crucial for establishing productive human-robot interaction and collaboration. The main goal of this module is to integrate a stereo camera setup that records RGB and Depth data in order to extract the live position of the human operator. With the use of a body tracking module based on neural networks, 3d keypoints that represent human joints and characteristics are identified. Figure 26 presents the joint of human body as visualized in RVIZ environment.

Figure 26. Human joints identification.

The approach consists of multiple critical steps. Initially, gathering data requires using a stereo camera system to collect high-resolution RGB and depth data. After that, an AI model is used by the body tracking module to identify the precise 3D position of each keypoint in real time. Every keypoint is also given a distinct identification that corresponds to a certain physical attribute. It has been determined that the head, chest, and arms of a human operator are among the body components most at danger of colliding with the robotic arm during normal robot operation. In order to reduce the amount of keypoints generated and keep just those that face immediate danger, a filtering process is put into place. This procedure improves operational efficiency by minimizing the number and size of messages and provides safety for human operators. As this module is built upon the ROS2 architecture subscribers are used to listen for the camera data and publishers for broadcasting the filtered keypoints. Furthermore, the AI model is capable of estimating partially occluded keypoints by using an integrated skeleton model of the user, also occlusions can further be eliminated by the use of multiple synchronized cameras to provide a unified and more robust human tracking system. Figure 27 presents the human tracking visualization after the filtering of human joints in relation to the real view of the operator in the robotic cell.

Figure 27. Human tracking visualization after the filtering process, (a) real workstation view, (b) RVIZ 2 environment.

2.4.3.2 Collision Avoidance

With a robust 3D human tracking system in place relative to the camera's frame of reference, it's essential to determine the camera's position relative to the robot's planning world frame. This is typically achieved by performing an eye-on-base calibration, which involves attaching a fiducial marker to the robot's end effector and taking a number of samples. This way the skeleton points can easily be transformed to the

robot's planning world frame. This calibration procedure needs to be performed only once even for mobile robots.

Using the MoveIt's low level libraries Moveitcpp it is possible to perform global planning while avoiding collision with the environment (Planning Scene) and other user defined path constraints. The collision objects present in the planning scene are separated into two categories, static object with respect to the robot and dynamic or moving collision objects belonging to the human worker. In the current implementation the 3d keypoints from the human tracking system are expanded into spheres for the planning scene, it is also possible, depending on the velocity of these keypoints the spheres to expand more in size in real-time.

When the robot receives a target position as a goal, a snapshot of the planning scene including the operator is taken into account for the global plan generation, if the user collision spheres intersect with the robot in the starting phase, this process is repeated. This global plan guarantees no collision with the static objects while also avoiding the operator in that instant.

Before the execution of the generated trajectory, the Allowed Collision Matrix (ACM) is updated to allow collisions with the environment and only look for collisions with the collision objects related to the operator, this is done to avoid false collision detections when the robot passes close from the static collision objects in the scene. Furthermore, n evenly spaced robot states along the trajectory points are generated, this robot states are used to determine if the operator is in contact with a future position of the robot along its trajectory.

While the robot is performing the trajectory, two collision detection threads are initiated. One is responsible to detect collisions between the operator and the real-time position of the robot while the other which is slower performs collision detection with all the future states of the robot along the trajectory, which are removed as the robot passes them. A collision is detected when the operator collision spheres have a distance from the robot meshes smaller than a threshold, to facilitate easier replanning after a collision.

If a collision is detected between the operator and a future position of the robot, the robot simply slows down using the functionality of the scaled joint trajectory controller or the speed scaling factor present in most robot controllers.

A collision between the operator and the actual robot triggers a pause to the trajectory execution, if the operator moves away within a certain time threshold for a certain time threshold, the robot continues its trajectory without modification, otherwise a global replan is initiated with a new trajectory avoiding the operator at this instant.

With this a sufficient collaborative planning and replanning is achieved. Figure 28 presents the calculated trajectory to avoid operator's hands during the assembly of the electrical cabinet for the KLEEMANN case. Future developments could include the ability of the robot to be compliant when paused or during the trajectory and to actively perform corrections along the trajectory to avoid the operator.

Figure 28. Trajectory calculation to avoid the operator's hands.

2.4.4 Role in pilot cases

In the KLEEMANN use case, task 4.5 supports the planning of movements for serial manipulators on AGVs. In this use case, the system is employed in the assembly of electrical cabinets, working alongside human operators to guarantee precise and adaptable positioning and attachment of components onto the panel. Moreover, it promotes seamless HRC by considering the condition of the human operator and implementing measures for collision avoidance.

In the DECATHLON use case, the motion planner coordinates pick-and-place movements for stationary serial manipulators to unload boxes containing different products.

In the AERNNOVA use case, the motion planner is not yet utilized/applicable.

2.5 Manual intervention for robot programming and control

2.5.1 Task overview

This task regards the different methods created for enabling the human operators to control and program the robots manually. Currently, the developments for this task are focused on the AR application (described in detail in Section 2.1), which was enhanced with new functionalities for robot control. These functionalities enable the operator to observe the robot and its future trajectories during the execution of an operation, configure several settings for the robot's movements and moving the robotic arm towards designated positions. Future work includes new methods for controlling both the robotic arms and the AGVs manually, along with new applications for smartwatch and tablet devices.

2.5.2 Adaptive human machine interaction & control

2.5.2.1 Introduction

To facilitate seamless and flexible manual robot control, several functionalities were developed in the AR application using the Unity3D platform. To enable the communication between the AR application and the robot, the ROS 2 framework was utilized. Initially, a TCP connection was established as described in Section 2.1.2.1. Through this connection, the AR application can send specific ROS 2

signals to the robot’s controller or specific ROS 2 components that have been developed for handling the execution of robot movements.

This section describes in detail the current methods of manual robot control through the AR interfaces and the provided robot settings configuration options. Section 2.5.2.2 is focused on the representation of the robotic arm and its trajectories during the execution. Section 2.5.2.3 describes the first method of manual robot control using an interactive robot hologram. Finally, Section 2.5.2.4 presents the different robot settings that the operator can adjust to control the robot’s function.

2.5.2.2 Robot representation and future trajectory visualization

To ensure the safety of the human-robot collaborative operation it was essential to provide information to the operator about the robot’s movements. This would increase the operator’s awareness and enable them to intervene and stop the execution of any movement. As a result, in cases the operator detects any dangers occurred by this movement, such as a potential collision between the robot and another object, they can immediately cancel the movement before the execution.

To achieve this functionality, a new implementation was developed that receives the information about the generated trajectories and visualize them on the operator’s viewport. To visualize the trajectory, initially, the robot model had to be imported to the AR application. For this purpose, a Unified Robotics Description Format (URDF) file was created for creating a digital version of the robot model. For the KLEEMANN case, the URDF file includes the RB-KAIROS mobile platform, the UR10e robotic arm and a ROBOTIQ electrical gripper. These components were used as an initial testbed and will be updated with the final equipment that will be used for the full KLEEMANN demonstrator. Consequently, the URDF file was imported into the AR application using the URDF Importer library by Unity Technologies. As a result, a new virtual object was created in the AR application with all the necessary information about the physics and the textures of the robot. This virtual object is visualized as a hologram in the AR viewport. To successfully visualize the future trajectories without the danger for the operator to confuse the real and the virtual robot, a new copy of the virtual hologram was created with blue semi-transparent texture. Figure 29 illustrates the real robot, the URDF in RVIZ2 environment and the two created holograms.

Figure 2929. Robot representation in AR application, (a) real robot, (b) URDF file in RVIZ2, (c) real robot hologram, (d) hologram of future trajectories.

These holograms were created to provide the operator with information about the robot's movements. However, in order to receive this necessary information from the robotic system, new ROS 2 components had to be developed. For this purpose, two ROS 2 subscribers were created. The first one was designed to receive the values of the joint states which correspond to the rotation of each joint of the robot. These values were received real-time during the execution, transformed into the coordinate system of Unity scene and then assigned to the joints of the first virtual robot. With this way, the virtual robot copies the movements of the real robot at runtime. By default, this hologram remains disabled, since the operator is able to observe the real robot with the AR glasses. However, the operator is able to enable the hologram's visibility to test if the application is properly connected with the robotic system and it receives successfully the required information.

The second ROS 2 subscriber has been created to receive the information of the future trajectories. This subscriber acquires this information each time the motion planner calculates a new trajectory towards a specified position. The generated plan is published through ROS 2 as a joint trajectory message. This message contains the positions and velocities for each joint throughout the whole robot movement. These values are used to update the blue trajectory hologram and provide the operator with a visual representation of the movement.

2.5.2.3 Manual robot control using interactive hologram

In many cases during the execution of an operation, the robot may require to be moved at a specific position, either for handling an exception such as a failed detection by a vision system or to be programmed by the operator for collecting predefined positions. For this purpose, the first method for controlling the robotic arm was developed. This method includes an interactive hologram similar to the ones described in the previous section. This hologram is a copy of the robot with another texture to be distinguished from the other two virtual robots. Superimposed on this hologram, there is also a 3D axis visual to help the operator to monitor the orientation of the hologram. This axis visual has been positioned on the robot's end effector and is moving along with the hologram.

In order to move the robot manually using this method, the following procedure must be followed. Initially, the operator interacts with the specific button either from the side or the hand menu. The interactive hologram with the 3D axis visual is enabled, along with an interface for sending the appropriate signals to the robotic system. This interface includes two buttons for sending the goal to calculate a trajectory and cancelling the current robot movement. The operator can interact with the 3D axis virtual object using a pinch gesture to grab and pull the hologram. With this way, the operator moves the end effector of the hologram and designates a specific final position for calculating a new trajectory. In order to visualize the interactive hologram, a new ROS 2 service was created. This service is responsible of calculating real-time the inverse kinematics of the robot to follow the movement of the end effector. While the operator moves the axis, a ROS 2 service client that has been developed on the AR application requests through the ROS 2 connection a new inverse kinematics solution for the new position. The ROS 2 service server that is running on the ROS workspace, performs the necessary mathematical transformation and provides the AR application with the specific value of each robot joint. The AR application assigns these values to the joints of the interactive hologram and updates the virtual object. The same process is repeated for each frame of the application. With this implementation, the operator can move the end effector of the interactive hologram and observe the pose of the robot for each designated destination position. When the operator is satisfied with the final position of the end effector can interact with the "Send Goal" button to send the appropriate ROS 2 action goal to the robotic system and enable the calculation of the trajectory. The motion planner of ROS workspace generates a

trajectory and using the hologram described in the previous section, the AR application visualizes the calculated plan. Consequently, the generated trajectory is executed, and the real robot moves towards the designated by the operator position. Throughout the duration of the movement, the operator can press the "Cancel" button to cancel the ROS 2 action goal and terminate the execution. Figure 3030 showcases the manual robot control implementation and the developed AR interfaces to interact with and execute the described process.

Figure 3030. Manual robot control using interactive hologram, (a) designating final position, (b) interface for sending signals to the robotic system.

2.5.2.4 Robot settings configuration

Another important functionality regarding the robot control from within the AR application is the robot settings configuration. In human-robot collaborative operations it is crucial for the operator to be able to adjust several factors for the robot, such as the speed or the acceleration of its movements. For this purpose, a new user interface was created. This interface can be accessed either by the side or the hand menu. The interface is presented in Figure 2 (b).

As shown in the figure, the interface contains two toggle buttons and two sliders. By interacting the toggle buttons, the operator can enable or disable the visibility of the two created holograms for the real robot representation and the future trajectory visualization, both explained in Section 2.5.2.2. Each time the operator interacts with the toggle button, the application searches for all the visual elements of the specific hologram. These elements are either enabled or disabled. With this way, the robot holograms are still active as virtual objects in the scene but they are not visualized in the application's viewport.

Utilizing the two sliders, the operator can adjust the speed and the acceleration of the robot's movements. Each time the value of these sliders is updated, a ROS 2 service call is sent by the AR application to the robot's hardware interface. This interface updates the corresponding setting real-time. The operator can even update these settings during the execution of a movement if needed. Future work will include adding more settings options for the operator to configure.

2.5.3 Role in pilot cases

The developments of this task will be utilized and demonstrated in the KLEEMANN and DECATHLON cases. In the KLEEMANN case, the AR application along with the smartwatch application will be used to manually control the robot, designate a specific path for its movement, and configure robot settings. In the DECATHLON case, a tablet application will be integrated to address exceptions in the production line by adding new products to the production information repository and performing several tasks to program the robot to handle these products.

3 Conclusions

In conclusion, this deliverable reports the prototypes of the WP4 and the initial version of the developments for tasks 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6.

In T4.2, AR interfaces were developed for providing operator support during the execution of human-robot collaborative applications. More specifically, two menu interfaces (side and hand menu) were developed for accessing the basic functionalities of the application. In order to localize the interfaces in relation to the robotic cell and the other real-world objects, a localization implementation was developed using QR code markers identification. Furthermore, specific interfaces were created for the human-assigned tasks and notifications for unexpected events. To enhance the seamless integration and collaboration with the robotic system, an AI-based vision system was created to detect the components grasped by the operator and send this information to the orchestration system automatically.

For T4.3, a motion planner was developed that calculates trajectories for the navigation of AGVs. This motion planning algorithms are able to generate adaptable and precise movements based on the Dynamic Motion Primitives. Also, a collision avoidance strategy was developed to enhance the safety of the navigation and avoid any potential dangers from collisions between the AGV and the human operators or other objects.

In T4.4, the CAD-based AI vision systems developed initially for T3.2 were combined in order to extract the required information for robot programming. More specifically, the grasping point estimation and the object detection modules were integrated to generate a ROS frame and move the robot for grasping the appropriate components. This task also includes the processes of the 3D CAD model processing, the simulated gripper projection and the extraction of suitable grasping points and the virtual scene creation for generating synthetic data, all of which are essential for the development of the grasping point estimation module in T3.2.

The progress of T4.5 include the developments of motion primitives for serial robots (robotic arms). This involves motion planning algorithms for precise trajectory generation, following collision avoidance techniques. The developed motion planner was also integrated with ROS, in order to create a MoveIt plugin, enabling the straightforward integration with other modules. Within the scope of this task, a human tracking and collision avoidance module was also developed. This implementation allows real-time detection of operators and enable robots to avoid them, increasing the safety of the operations.

Regarding T4.6, the AR application was enhanced with new functionalities for manual robot control and robot settings configuration. Initially, AR holograms were created from the robot model to visualize the real robot and future trajectories. The first method for controlling the robot from within the application was also implemented using an interactive hologram to designate the final position of the robot's movement. To enhance the robot control and provide more options to the operator, new interfaces were developed for adjusting robot settings such as speed and acceleration of its movements.

The developed functionalities will be integrated to support the full demonstrators of the three MASTERLY use cases. Future reporting of these developments includes D4.3 which will be focused on the final version of the developments and D4.4 which will involve the action for integrating these functionalities with other modules. Some of these developments will also be reported in D5.4, which will describe their integration with the workflow controller as the orchestration system. The next milestone for these developments is MS4: "Final prototypes of MASTERLY enabling technologies", which is scheduled for M36.

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